

Risk assessment of Landslide Area, Mapping by GIS & Remote Sensing and its Mitigation Methods for Patan Taluka (Western ghat in Maharashtra)

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Abstract: *In many parts of India, particularly in the Himalayas, the northeastern hill ranges, and the Western Ghats, landslides are one of the most significant hydro geological risks. Natural disasters that frequently occur and cause property damage and fatalities include landslides. GIS and remote sensing are strong methods that can be very helpful in reducing the risk of landslides. Landslides are recognized both historically and currently through the use of remote sensing and GIS. Reliable methods for mitigation of landslide impacts must be based on the latest developments in knowledge and advanced methods of analysis and synthesis. An interdisciplinary approach is essential for effective solutions to landslide problems. Prevention or mitigation of landslide disasters requires understanding the factors which often lead to catastrophic landsliding and the simulation of conditions under which such failures may occur. Landslide risk management requires understanding and assessment of susceptibility and hazard. In particular, for regional assessment, landslide susceptibility and hazard mapping and zonation are necessary. Mitigation of landslide impacts is facilitated by the use of research -based thresholds of rainfall pore water pressure and/or displacement. These thresholds can be used for the development and application of early warning systems. Monitored data on landslide movements and pore water pressures can be very useful for updating hazard and risk scenarios. Such data also contribute to the capacity for landslide management in near real-time. This outcome directly confirms the applicability and accuracy of the integrated remote sensing identification technology in the study area. The research results presented in this paper provide an effective scientific and theoretical basis for the monitoring and treatment of landslide geological disasters in the future stages. They also play a pivotal role in the prevention of such disasters*

KEYWORDS: *Landslide Hotspot, mapping, remote sensing and GIS, Landsat 8, DEM, Weighted Overlay etc.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the middle of the 20th century, with the continuous growth of the world population and the gradual expansion of the scope of human activities, coupled with the impact of global climate change and other factors, landslides have occurred more and more frequently, resulting in increasing economic losses and casualties. Landslides occur in almost all mountain areas with human habitation and engineering activities worldwide, which has become the type of geological disaster with the highest frequency and the most Since the middle of the 20th century, with the continuous growth of the world population and the gradual expansion of the scope of human activities, coupled with the impact of global climate change and other factors, landslides have occurred more and more frequently, resulting in increasing economic losses and casualties. [1] Landslides occur in almost all mountain areas with human habitation and engineering activities worldwide, which has become the type of geological disaster with the highest frequency and the most significance losses. Serious landslides not only cause great losses to the lives and property of local residents but also seriously affect the safe operation of railways, highways, and other infrastructure and

seriously hinder the development of the regional economy. [2] Therefore, the study of landslide geological disasters has important theoretical and practical value. Due to increased extreme rainstorms caused by global climate change, landslide disasters have become more severe. Therefore, there is a need for an efficient method to identify potential landslides. Remote sensing technology has been widely used in geological disaster risk management for over 60 years. Optical remote sensing dominated the field, but now there is integrated remote sensing using various means such as spectrum and geometric measurement. High-resolution optical remote sensing data with sub-meter resolution can accurately detect landslide forms and hazardous environments. [3]

1.1 Movement of land during landslides:

The movement of land during a landslide is a complex process influenced by various factors such as slope gradient, geological conditions, soil composition, water content, and external triggers. Landslides involve the downslope movement of rock, soil, and debris, and their behavior can vary widely depending on the specific circumstances. There are three major variables that influence the kind and pace of mass waste on the Earth's surface.

- Slope gradient: The higher the land's slope, the more probable mass wasting will occur.
- Slope consolidation: Sediments, as well as broken or weakly cemented rocks and sediments, are weak and prone to mass wasting Water
- Saturated slope materials may lose cohesiveness and flow freely.
- The motion of a heterogeneous mass comprising water (snow), soil, and rocks is intricate and does not match the flow of a homogeneous and Newtonian fluid.

1.2 Factors Which Affect Present Study Area:

The occurrence of landslides includes a number of factors. The major natural factors responsible for causing landslides are discussed below. [4]

- a) Geology-** Landslide occurrences are influenced by geological structure. For landslides, active faults are more significant. Sliding is influenced by the nature and structure of the rock. Cohesion-less particles, such as coarse gravel, are more likely to migrate than cohesive materials, such as clay and silt. Major geological characteristics needed for the development of landslides in the research region include steeply sloped bedding planes, joints, fractures, fissures, and other zones of weakness, as well as the existence of an active fault and a stratified structural arrangement of rocks.
- b) Lithology -** Rock with a softer tone. Landslides are more likely to occur in salts, shales, and clays. This sort of soft laterite was also discovered in the research area. When extra precipitation occurs and more weight is placed on these weaker rocks, they will collapse considerably sooner than tougher rocks. These parameters are crucial in defining the shear strength, permeability, susceptibility to chemical and physical weathering, and other properties of soil and rock materials, all of which influence stability.
- c) Gravity -** Mass movement is defined as the separation of a mass of earth or rock from its height down a slope under the effect of gravity. Due to excessive cutting of sides for traffic circulation, the similar scenario may be seen in study region. Gravity is the primary cause of mass motions. Landslides usually caused by shear collapse of the rock o that forms the slope.
- d) Slope-** Slope is a visible and vital aspect of the environment, especially in hilly and mountainous areas. Due to excessive cutting of sides for traffic circulation, the similar scenario exists in the

studied area. Slopes appear to be stable and static, yet they are actually dynamically developing systems. The angle of slope determines the earth's stability and instability. Because of its unstable nature, steep slopes are more prone to landslides, and vice versa. Increased angle of slope causes more landslide threats in our research location.

- e) **Vegetation**- In our location, vegetation is an important component that has a considerable impact in the incidence of landslides. Our region's vegetation is mostly made up of trees that do not hold soil, resulting in the production of loose pockets, which in turn leads to the construction of fault planes. A forest shields the surface from the weathering effects of sunlight, rain, and winds, while also retaining a significant quantity of water by saturating the broad vegetative surface. Deforestation also exposes the soil to direct rainfall effect due to its existence. Plant roots spread as they grow in rock joints, cracks, fractures, and fissures. The spread of the plant's roots and progressive enlargement of the stem expands the joints or cracks, causing physical weathering of the rocks. As a result, the fragmented rock mass begins to move downhill under the power of gravity. The disintegrated rock mass in this way start moving downward under the influence of gravity. In the monsoon season due to high rainfall vegetation takes-up large quantity of water and add weight on steep slope.
- f) **Earthquakes** -An earthquake is caused by a variety of events occurring under the earth's surface, including the bending and faulting of the earth's crust, volcanic eruptions, plate movements, and the hydro static pressure bursting of man-made dams and water bodies. The existence of a small dam in the study region contributes to the landslide by causing minor vibrations caused by dam pressure. Earthquakes have two effects on slope stability: first, they increase shear stress, and second, they diminish the resistance of rocks and slope materials. Landslides are caused by the joints, fractures, and fissures created by earthquakes.
- g) **Flash Floods** - Flash floods occur when a previously dry valley has a sudden surge in flow. They're frequently connected with significant volumes of water and/or sediment being transported quickly. Flash floods are caused by a rapid and severe deluge of water in a river's catchment basin. Flooding is the natural phenomenon of over bank flow. Floods can be caused by natural or manmade events such as heavy rains, cloudbursts, and the melting of snow and ice in river catchment areas, or the blocking of a river by a landslide, followed by a sudden release of water, the breaking of a dam or reservoir, and a large amount of siltation in rivers, which can raise the water level.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The focus is on landslide hazards affecting various regions in India, notably the Himalayas, North-eastern hill ranges, Western Ghats, Nilgiris, Eastern Ghats, and Vindhya.

Sunita Devi, January (2020) study underscores the devastating impact of landslides, exemplified by the 1968 Darjeeling floods. Morphological, geological, and anthropological factors contribute to landslide occurrences. Remote Sensing and GIS emerge as powerful tools for landslide mitigation, aiding in past and present recognition, monitoring, spatial and temporal analysis, early response, rescue efforts, forecasting, and warnings. The spatial resolution of around 10m is crucial for effective landslide feature recognition, with various satellite imagery options discussed. The comprehensive review categorizes remote sensing techniques into three phases: detection and classification, monitoring, and spatial-temporal analysis and prediction of slope failures

Praveen B. Gawali, (2017), the escalating threat of rainfall-triggered landslides in the Western Ghats prompts a proactive approach to identify susceptible areas. The research focuses on the Kalsubai region in Maharashtra, India, utilizing eight weighted parameters—rainfall, slope, lithology, land use and land cover (LULC), soil properties, relative relief, aspect, and lineament. Advanced remote sensing (RS) data and geospatial techniques in GIS and image processing software are employed. Among 59 villages, 9 are categorized as very high risk, 13 as high, 12 as moderate, 11 as low, and 14 as very low. The study highlights heavy rains and steep slopes, exacerbated by anthropogenic activities, as dominant landslide triggers. The created spatial and non-spatial database aids in effective prevention and mitigation strategies, offering a cost-effective methodology applicable to other landslide-prone areas.

Sandip S. Sathe, (2019), the catastrophic landslide on July 30, 2014, in Malingaon village, Maharashtra, India, resulting in the burial of around 140 people, is analyzed. Soil samples from different hill slope sections were examined to determine soil properties and slope stability. Excessive rainfall triggered the landslide, impacting geotechnical soil properties. Results indicated an unstable hill slope with a factor of safety less than one, making it susceptible to failure. Land use and land cover map analysis revealed instability, attributed to unscientific agricultural practices and nonagricultural land conversion. The study proposes viable technical solutions to prevent similar disasters in comparable topographical features.

Abhishek A. Wadate, (2022), study centers around the area of a previous landslide in Mahabaleshwar, with geology identified as the primary contributor to landslide risk. Landslides, significant natural disasters, pose threats in mountainous terrains like Maharashtra's Western Ghats. Utilizing Geographical Information Systems (GIS), the research employs multi-criteria modeling and weighted overlay methods in ArcGIS 10.3 software for landslide-prone zone mapping. The study's outcomes serve as valuable tools for engineers, planners, and administrators, aiding in the implementation of necessary mitigation and adaptation measures in the region.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Landslides in Patan Taluka are primarily triggered by a combination of steep terrain, complex geological formations, and heavy monsoon rainfall. The steep slopes make the region susceptible to gravitational forces, while the intricate geological structure, including rock types and fault lines, influences slope stability. Intense and prolonged rainfall saturates the soil, reducing its cohesion and triggering mass movements. Human activities such as deforestation and improper land use further exacerbate the risk. These factors collectively contribute to the occurrence of landslides, posing a continuous threat to the safety of the local community and the region's infrastructure. In India many of the research work is completed in the Northern and Southern parts. The western ghat in Maharashtra is studied by various researchers. Too many papers are available but we want to focus part of Patan Taluka which is very high landslide prone area and high rainfall area. The impact of rainfall on Patan Taluka is profound, especially during the monsoon season. The region, nestled in the Western Ghats, experiences heavy and sustained rainfall, leading to heightened risks of landslides and flooding. The steep slopes and complex terrain make Patan Taluka highly vulnerable to soil erosion and mass wasting. This intense rainfall not only poses threats to human settlements, agriculture, and infrastructure but also contributes to environmental challenges such as habitat disruption and soil degradation. Effective management

strategies are crucial to mitigate the adverse effects of rainfall in Patan Taluka and ensure the resilience of the local community.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Figure 1. Flow Chart of Methodology

5. STUDY AREA

The area under investigation is situated in the Satara district of Patan, covering coordinates between latitudes $17^{\circ}37'35''$ N and longitudes $73^{\circ}54'00''$ E, with an area of approximately 1385.82 square kilometers. Its average elevation stands at 582 meters (1909 feet). Patan, a significant location within this area, is positioned at coordinates $17^{\circ} 20' N$, $73^{\circ} 50' E$, approximately 24 kilometers southeast of RS Karad, along the Karad-Kumbharli road. The climate of the investigated area is characterized as arid to semi-arid, with heavy rainfall during the rainy season, relatively lesser precipitation in summer, and heavy rainfall again during winter. Rainfall predominantly occurs as heavy showers with prolonged durations. The presence of the Koyana and Tarali dams, constructed on the Koyana and Tarali rivers respectively, adds to the hydrological significance of the area. Furthermore, the Sahyadri Mountain range intersects the study area, contributing to heavy rainfall and subsequently increasing the probability of landslides. The terrain features slopes ranging from flat at the top to steep at the plateau scarp, with slopes often being steep to vertical, making them susceptible to erosion and landslide occurrences. Rainfall exhibits significant variation, with the wet season starting in June and concluding in September, peaking during July and August. [5]

6. DATA COLLECTION

1. **Toposheet** - Toposheets are invaluable for hikers, backpackers, and outdoor enthusiasts as they facilitate navigation through unfamiliar terrain. They also serve as essential tools for scientists, urban planners, and geographers, providing a comprehensive understanding of the physical and cultural characteristics of a region. Military operations also heavily depend on toposheets for strategic planning, terrain analysis, and navigation in unfamiliar territories. Educationally, toposheets are valuable tools for teaching geography, cartography, and earth sciences. They provide a tangible way for students to understand and interpret spatial information. [6]

Figure 2. Toposheet of Patan Taluka

2. **Shapefile** –A shapefile is a geospatial vector data format commonly used in Geographic Information System (GIS) software. Developed by Esri, the shapefile format comprises a set of files that collectively store both geometric and attribute data for geographic features. These features can be points, lines, or polygons, representing discrete locations, connected sequences, or enclosed areas, respectively. [7] The format includes files with extensions like .shp (geometry), .shx (shape index), and .dbf (attribute data). Shapefiles also contain information about the coordinate system and projection, ensuring accurate spatial representation.

Figure 3. Shapefiles of Taluka in satara district

3. **Landsat 8** - Landsat 8, launched on February 11, 2013, stands as a critical milestone in Earth observation, serving as a testament to the joint efforts of NASA and the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS). Initially designated as the Landsat Data Continuity Mission (LDCM), this satellite has significantly advanced our capacity to monitor and understand Earth's dynamics. Its two primary instruments, the Operational Land Imager (OLI) camera and the Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS), have proven instrumental in the study of Earth's surface temperature and its implications for global warming.

Figure 4.Landsat 8

4. **Digital Elevation Model (DEM)** - A Digital Elevation Model (DEM) serves as a digital representation of the Earth's topographic surface, specifically focusing on the bare ground without incorporating elements such as trees, buildings, or other surface objects. DEM construction involves utilizing diverse data sources. Historically, the United States Geological Survey (USGS) primarily derived DEMs from traditional topographic maps.[8]

Figure 5.DEM Image of Patan Taluka

- 5. Rainfall data-** Typically, rainfall is expressed in millimeters (mm). These units are used to indicate the depth of rainfall accumulation over a certain region. Different temporal and spatial resolutions (point-based or gridded) can be used to collect rainfall data (hourly, daily, monthly, etc.) Precipitation patterns can be studied in greater detail using high-resolution data. The Centre for Hydrometeorology and Remote Sensing (CHRS) provided the rainfall data in this instance. According to a study of rainfall data from 2000 to 2022, the district's typical annual rainfall ranges from 66.86 to 762 mm. The basic relationship between rainfall depth (say, mm) and volume is thus: 1 mm of rainfall depth amounts to 1 L of rainwater per m². One centimetre of rainfall corresponds to a volume of water equivalent to 10 L falling over an area of one meter².

Figure 6. Rain Data of Satara District

- 6. Composite Band-**After downloaded the landsat 8 images, it can open in Arcmap software. There are total 11 bands but here we required only 7 bands for any work. We can't work on 7 band each so this seven-band convert into one band i.e. Composite Band. Composite band means conversion of multiple layer of bands into one layer for multiple work.

Figure 7. Composite Band

7. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

7.1 Extract Map by Study Area

In this, we want to extract the Patan Taluka From whole Landsat 8 and DEM image i.e. Extract by Mask.In Geoprocessing tool, go to the Arctool Box, click on Spatial Analyst Tool then click on Extract by Mask. Extracts the cells of a raster that correspond to the areas defined by a mask.Extraction is the action of removing something part from whole part. [9]

Figure 8. Extract for Landsat 8

Figure 9. Extract for DEM File

7.2 Euclidean distance

Euclidean distance in ArcMap is a spatial analysis technique used to calculate the straight-line distance between points in a geographic dataset. In ArcMap, this tool is accessible through the Spatial Analyst toolbox, allowing users to perform distance calculations on both raster and vector data. The resulting output is often presented as a continuous surface, where each cell or pixel represents its Euclidean distance from specified source locations. The Euclidean distance raster will provide information about how far each location is from the nearest stream. Here we provide

Euclidean Distance only Stream & Road Data because both files are Vector Format. E.D. provide only Vector file format not Raster Format. [10]

Figure 10. Euclidean distance for Stream

➤ **Steps to Calculate Euclidean Distance for Slope/Road in ArcMap:**

1. **Open ArcMap** and load map data into the software.

2. **Locate the Euclidean Distance Tool:**

Go to ArcToolbox > Spatial Analyst Tools > Distance > Euclidean Distance.

3. **Run the Tool:**

Once we have set the input parameters, run the tool. ArcMap will process the data and generate the Euclidean distance raster.

Figure 11. Euclidean distance for Road

5.3 Reclassification

a) Reclassify slope

1. Open ArcMap and load elevation data (Digital Elevation Model - DEM). Navigate to the "Spatial Analyst" toolbox: ArcToolbox > Spatial Analyst Tools > Surface > Slope. In the Slope tool, input DEM as the input raster and specify an output raster location and name.

2. Choose an appropriate method for calculating slope (e.g., “PERCENT”).Run the tool. With the newly created slope raster, go to the “Spatial Analyst “toolbar and choose “Reclassify”
3. In the Reclassify dialog, input the slope raster as the input raster.
4. Define the slope ranges for each category.
5. Assign appropriate values to each category. Click "OK" to reclassify the slope raster.

Figure 12. Reclassify of Slope Analysis

b) Reclassify Stream Analysis

Reclassification of a Stream Map is a GIS process where categorical values assigned to different features in the map, specifically those representing streams or water bodies, are modified to meet specific analysis or mapping objectives. This transformation involves assigning new classifications to stream segments based on attributes like flow intensity, water quality, or ecological significance. By reclassifying, the map becomes a more tailored and informative tool for various applications, including hydrological modeling, land-use planning, and environmental management. For example, reclassifying streams based on water quality parameters can help identify areas requiring conservation efforts or pollution control. [11]

Figure 13. Reclassify Stream Analysis

c) Reclassify NDVI Analysis

Reclassifying a Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) map involves categorizing or grouping the NDVI values into different classes or intervals. Its use for analysis of vegetation health. NDVI values typically range from -1 to 1, where: Values near -1 represent non-vegetated surfaces (e.g., water bodies). Values close to 0 indicate bare soil or urban areas. Positive values, especially higher ones, indicate healthy vegetation.

Figure 14. Reclassify NDVI Analysis

d) Reclassify Road Analysis

Reclassifying roads in ArcMap involves the modification of attribute values in either raster or vector datasets to categorize or redefine road features based on specific criteria. In raster data, the “Reclassify” tool in the “Spatial Analyst Tools” is employed. This tool allows users to assign new values to existing ones, enabling the reclassification of roads based on chosen criteria such as condition, type, or other attributes. [12]

Figure 15. Reclassify of Road Analysis

5.4 Weighted Overlay Method

The overlay method plays a crucial role in landslide analysis in ArcMap by facilitating the integration and analysis of various spatial datasets to identify areas susceptible to landslides. Using the weighted overlay technique for landslide analysis, incorporating various overlay tools such as fuzzy overlay, fuzzy membership, weighted overlay, and weighted sum. Choose weighted overlay for the analysis from ArcTool box. Input Data Layers are RoadReclassify, Stream reclassify, NDVI, Slope reclassify data. NDVI is assigned the highest weightage (35%). Slope and streams are considered equally important, each assigned 25% weightage. & roads are (15%). The total weightage should sum up to 100%.The output is classified into 1 to 6 parts. Adjust the colour scheme to enhance the visibility of risky areas. Assigning colours in that clearly distinguishes risk levels makes hotspots easily identifiable. Click “OK” to generate the final analysis output on the screen. The color scheme chosen effectively highlights the risk parts of the output. Using contrasting colors to make the hotspots clearly visible.

Figure 16. Risk Assessment (Landslide Hotspot)

Table no. 1 Landslide Susceptibility

Sr no	Susceptibility	Area(Sq.km)	Percentage Area %
1	Critical	0.4409	0.00033
2	Very high	35.566	2.6499
3	high	227.826	16.745
4	Moderate	528.91	38.736
5	low	521.768	38.150
6	Very low	49.605	3.7166

Figure 17: Graph of Landslide Susceptibility

5.5 Maps Required For Landslide Hotspot

A. **DEM:** Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) help assess landslide risk by identifying steep slopes, areas prone to erosion, and drainage patterns, providing crucial data for landslide susceptibility mapping and risk mitigation planning.

Figure A. DEM Map

B. Slope map: its provide essential data for assessing landslide risk by highlighting areas with steep slopes, which are more susceptible to instability and erosion. Slopemaphelp identify regions where landslides are likely to occur, aiding in hazard mapping and risk management strategies. [13]

Figure B. Slope Map

C. Stream map: it is valuable in assessing landslide risk by indicating drainage patterns and areas prone to water accumulation. They help identify regions where water flow might increase soil saturation, leading to instability and triggering landslides.

Figure C. Stream Map

D. NDVI map: Normalized Difference Vegetation Index can indirectly aid in assessing landslide risk by indicating vegetation health and density. Higher NDVI values typically correspond to healthier vegetation cover, which can stabilize slopes and reduce landslide susceptibility. Conversely, areas with low NDVI values may indicate sparse vegetation cover, potentially indicating higher landslide risk due to soil erosion and reduced slope stability.[14]

Figure D. NDVI Map

5.6 Landslide Mitigation Method

Landslides pose a recurrent hazard to human life and livelihood in most parts of the world, especially in some regions that have experienced rapid population and economic growth. Hazards are mitigated mainly through precautionary means—for instance, by restricting or even removing populations from areas with a history of landslides, by restricting certain types of land use where slope stability is in question, and by installing early warning systems based on the monitoring of ground conditions such as strain in rocks and soils, slope displacement, and groundwater levels. There are also various direct methods of preventing landslides; these include modifying slope geometry, using chemical agents to reinforce slope material, installing structures such as piles and retaining walls, grouting rock joints and fissures, diverting debris pathways, and rerouting surface and underwater drainage. Such direct methods are constrained by cost, landslide magnitude and frequency, and the size of human settlements at risk. Mitigation refers to the action of reducing the severity, impact, or risk of something undesirable or harmful. In various contexts such as disaster management, environmental protection, and risk assessment, mitigation involves implementing measures or strategies to prevent, minimize, or control adverse outcomes or events. These measures are typically aimed at reducing vulnerability, enhancing resilience, and improving overall safety and well-being. Mitigation efforts often involve proactive planning, resource allocation, and

implementation of policies, technologies, and practices to mitigate potential hazards or risks. Mitigation methods for landslides aim to reduce the risk and impact of landslides on human lives, infrastructure, and the environment. [15, 16]

Here are some common mitigation techniques:

- **Land Use Planning and Zoning**
Implementing regulations and zoning restrictions to prevent development in landslide-prone areas can help mitigate the risk. This involves identifying high-risk areas through geological surveys and maps.
- **Vegetation Management**
Planting and maintaining vegetation on slopes can help stabilize soil and reduce erosion, thus decreasing the likelihood of landslides. Root systems help bind soil together and absorb water, reducing surface runoff.
- **Terracing and Slope Stabilization**
Constructing retaining walls, terraces, or embankments on slopes can help stabilize them and reduce the risk of slope failure. This involves engineering solutions such as soil nails, rock bolts, and retaining structures.
- **Surface Drainage Control**
Proper drainage systems can divert excess water away from slopes, reducing saturation and erosion, which are common triggers for landslides. Installing surface water management features such as ditches, culverts, and surface channels can help control water flow.
- **Early Warning Systems**
Implementing monitoring systems such as inclinometers, piezometers, and ground-based or satellite-based radar can help detect slope movements and provide early warnings to residents and authorities.
- **Education and Awareness**
Educating communities about the risks of landslides, signs of slope instability, and appropriate emergency response measures can help reduce vulnerability and improve preparedness.
- **Erosion Control**
Implementing erosion control measures such as erosion blankets, silt fences, and check dams can help prevent soil erosion, reducing the likelihood of landslide initiation.
- **Emergency Preparedness and Response**
Developing emergency response plans and ensuring that residents are aware of evacuation routes and safety procedures can help minimize casualties and damage in the event of a landslide.
- **Reforestation and Rehabilitation**
Restoring degraded slopes through reforestation and rehabilitation efforts can help stabilize soil and prevent erosion, reducing landslide risk over the long term.

6. CONCLUSION

- Now a day's weather condition on the earth surface is changing very drastically. The rainfall conditions are also changed. The rainfall percentage is increasing. The landslides are mostly occurred where heavy rainfall, large slope, soil properties suitable to landslide, areas having water sources, low vegetation index. There is need to study the landslide susceptibility and mapping.
- In this thesis, we conclude that we can find the landslide hotspots by using the arc GIS software. The software will give the landslide prone areas according to the geographical information system. By integrating spatial data and advanced analytical capabilities, ArcGIS enables researchers to assess the susceptibility of different regions to landslides effectively.
- If we are getting the accurate results for the prediction of landslide then it will very helpful for the mitigation planning of the landslide prone areas. Some of the areas in the analysis are such that there is high population so there should be awareness between the people that the area they are living is landslide prone area so that in the heavy rainfall they will take proper precautions.
- Sustained development requires continued vigilance and perennial attention in respect of landslide risk management. Notwithstanding this, absolute slope safety is not practical or achievable due to many uncertainties inherent in the variables including geological settings, properties of soil and rock, rainfall pattern and groundwater conditions. Hence, it is necessary to promote an accurate understanding of the nature of landslip danger in order to enable the public to develop a realistic expectation for slope safety. This would reduce the likelihood of public over-reaction in future landslips and maintain community's support and trust in the implementation of the landslip prevention and mitigation works.
- The research shows that land use land cover, rainfall, slope, stream, NDVI plays an important role in landslide triggering. Total study area is divided into 6 zones i.e. critical, very high, high, moderate, low, very low comprising of 0.00033% , 2.649 % , 16.745 % , 38.736 % , 38.150 % , 3.7166 %

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